

RELATIONS BETWEEN LIFE SATISFACTION AND PROFESSIONAL DETERMINANTS AND SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS AMONG PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS

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Abstract

The aim of the study reported in this paper was to examine life satisfaction among physical education teachers, as well as to look for relationships of its level within selected parameters related to the occupation of teaching and socio-cultural factors.

The research applied to a group of 99 physical education teachers from the Opolskie Voivodeship. The Polish adaptation of the SWLS life satisfaction scale was employed for this purpose [10]. An original survey questionnaire developed by this author was also used, as it enabled the determination of the ways in which free time is spent and the duration of time per day when the interviewed subjects sit for excessively long periods.

The study did not demonstrate statistically significant dependences between the gender of the subjects as well as their level of education and the investigated parameters. Most teachers reported a high (55.6%) level of life satisfaction, whereas average satisfaction was reported by 41.4 % of the subjects, and by a few as low as 3%.

The study did not reveal any statistically significant correlations between life satisfaction and age, work experience nor the time spent in a sitting position. Only 46.5% of the teachers stated that if they had more free time for themselves, they would embark on some form of physical activity among other tasks. The subjects who declared working longer hours more often stated that they are willing to take various forms of rest excluding physical activity.

For the reasons outlined above, it seems necessary to encourage physical activity among physical education teachers as a manner of expending free time. Further research should strive to determine the factors responsible for life satisfaction among a variety of factors, not just socio-cultural, professional, or economic ones, with a note that such a study should involve a larger population.

Key words: *life satisfaction, teachers, public health*

Introduction

In the culture of hedonism which undoubtedly prevails nowadays, we are likely to place exciting experiences at the center of focus as they increasingly become the goals followed in human aspirations. Quality of life, the level of satisfaction in meeting human needs, and well-being in a biological dimension, as well as in a psychosocial one, play an increasingly important role in post-modern societies on both the local, regional and national scale. Satisfied people and employees perform duties at work more efficiently. Spiritual leaders with a specialty in cultivating joy and happiness, such as Nhat Hanh and Wernicke state that only happy teachers can change the world [13].

Physical education teachers form a specific group of persons who perform duties at school. Their lessons provide students with the ability to express emotions in a loud and uninhibited manner. Competition, movement, large space, joy and laughter form the main factors which distinguish PE activities from other lessons. By implementing games, PE teachers offer the ability to experience success and endure defeat, and bring students into the world of satisfying experiences, teach free time organizations, encourage work on one's health and experience satisfaction by realizing challenges and goals related to health, body and physical fitness. Therefore, it seems necessary that teachers have satisfactory experience not only in these

selected areas of life, but that their overall level of life satisfaction should be high as well.

Life satisfaction is defined by the author of the research tool used in this work as a general assessment of satisfaction with one's own achievements and living conditions [3]. Since it forms a concept that is difficult to clearly define, Veenhoven identifies it as an equivalent of happiness, and states that it represents the level at which an individual assesses the overall quality of their life, and how much they enjoy their lives [19].

Ehrhardt et al. [5] consider that life satisfaction is a subjective state of mind and can be measured only by asking people simple direct questions in various forms, e.g. questionnaire surveys.

The search for the sources of life satisfaction undoubtedly forms an important task of the social sciences. It has been proven that there are dependencies between life satisfaction and emotional intelligence, self-efficacy and healthy ways of coping with stress [7]. Identifying teacher satisfaction forms an important aspect from the point of view of their attitudes to work, satisfaction with it and the ability not to transfer emotional states from the workplace to one's private life [8].

The objective of the research reported in this paper was to examine the life satisfaction of physical education teachers as well as look for dependencies between its level and the selected occupational conditions and socio-cultural factors.

Material and Methods

The study involved a group of 99 physical education teachers from the Opolskie Voivodeship participating in methodological conferences organized by the teachers' vocational development service. The mean age of the subjects was 41.3 years (64 women and 35 men). The interviewees work at various levels of education – 44 subjects are employed in primary schools, 30 in middle school and 25 work in secondary schools. The mean length of service in the teaching profession was 15.9 years at the time of the surveys.

An anonymous auditorium-based study was conducted for the purposes of this work. To assess the level of life satisfaction, the authors applied the SWLS– Satisfaction with Life Scale developed by Diener et al. [3]. The Polish adaptation of this tool was carried out by Juczyński [10]. It forms a questionnaire comprising 5 statements, and the role of the interviewed subject was to evaluate them on a scale from 1 to 7 to express the extent to which each of the statements relates to their personal experience. The total of the values of all statements gives an overall indicator of life satisfaction. The results of the test were found to be in the range from 5 to 35 points. The higher the value of the indicator, the higher the level of life satisfaction. In accordance with the procedure recommended by the author of the research tool, the overall indicator was transformed onto a sten scale. The results in the range of 1 to 4 sten were interpreted as low, 5 to 6 sten as average, and 7 to 10 sten as high. The reliability of the SWLS test determined on the basis of the Crombach alpha was found to be 0.83 (the author of the Polish adaptation of this research tool determined the reliability of the test to be at the level of 0.81).

The scope of the test described above was supplemented by the application of the results of an original questionnaire developed by this author. The open interview included questions related to such issues as preferred ways of spending free time if more time was available to spare. Teachers were also asked to determine how much time (in minutes) they spend in a sitting position per day. The questionnaire was also designed to assess the basic characteristics of the subjects, including their age, gender, length of professional service and the level of education at which the subjects worked.

The material that was collected was subsequently subjected to statistical analysis using the MS Office Excel 2016 calculation sheet and Statistica 12 software. The Non-parametric Mann-Whitney U-test was applied with the purpose of evaluating the differences between the analyzed variables. The relations between the analyzed variables were calculated using the Kendall tau correlation. The analysis applied the

significance level to be represented by the effects for which the probability value was lower from the assumed level of significance equal to 0.05 ($p < 0.05$).

Results

The mean value of the life satisfaction index among the interviewed group of teachers was 24.1 points. The results did not justify the statement regarding statistically significant differentiation between the gender of the subjects. After converting the raw test results into stems, a mean value of 6.72 was obtained for the entire population of the examined subjects,

which means that teachers are characterized by a score that shows a level of life satisfaction that is slightly above average. The structure of satisfaction index levels (low, average, high) is summarized in Figure 1. The greatest number of subjects reported a high level of satisfaction (55.6%), whereas a slightly smaller proportion reported a high satisfaction (41.4%) and the smallest ratio of teachers recorded low life satisfaction (3.0%). The differences between the levels of the analyzed variables in both gender groups were found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Level of life satisfaction of examined physical education teachers

After a qualitative analysis of the variety of forms and ways of spending free time declared by the surveyed subjects was carried out, two categories of teachers were identified: those representing an active way of spending free time and those reporting a passive way of spending free time. Among men who recognize the role of active recreation (37.1%), the most common activities listed in the questionnaire included: training, physical activity, sports, physical recreation, cycling and running. However, for the majority of them, the availability of more free time would most likely involve spending time on relaxation excluding physical activity (62.9%), such as meeting friends or family. In this respect,

the replies from the interviewed women provided different results. On the basis of these replies, we can estimate that the majority of them (51.6%) intend to spend their free time actively, as the list of activities provided by the subjects included: fitness, gym exercises, swimming, running, mountaineering, and bicycle trips. We can note that men expressed their preferences more vaguely, in comparison to more focussed statements by the interviewed women who offered a more specific list physical of activities, and many of them listed several different disciplines, which was unlike the men. Besides, nearly half of the surveyed women (48.4%) declared their intention of spending free time

passively. Most frequently, this list included reading books or relaxing in the spa, as well as travelling. In addition, the surveyed subjects declared that on average they spent 191 minutes a day sitting down in the week preceding study. In this respect, there were no significant statistical differences depending on the gender of the interviewees.

In terms of the manner in which they spend free time (physically active vs. passive) the results of the subjects were not found to vary depending on factors such as the level of education at which they teach, the amount of time that is spent in a sitting position per day nor the level of life satisfaction. The only statistically

significant difference was reported in the case of the length of professional service ($Z=2.821$; $p = 0.004$). Teachers who plan to spend their free time passively are characterized by longer years of professional service. Besides, the analysis did not reveal statistically significant correlations between life satisfaction and such variables as: age, length of professional service, the level of education at which the subjects worked nor the time spent in a sitting position per day. However, with age and longer work experience, the amount of time spent in a sitting position tended to increase; however the correlation is statistically not significant, see Table 1.

Table 1. Correlations between the analyzed variables

Variables	age	level of education	professional experience	sedentary lifestyle
age				
level of education	0.0657			
professional experience	0.7982*	0.0514		
sedentary lifestyle	0.1529*	-0.0556	0.1509*	
SWLS	-0.0409	0.0050	-0.0067	-0.0831

Discussion

In Poland, statistics have provided information regarding a systematic increase in life satisfaction for many years. Recent surveys by the public opinion research center CBOS demonstrate a record high ratio of the population in Poland satisfied with their lives (80%). Life satisfaction is mainly determined by the personal assessment of the financial situation [20]. The course of professional experience also plays a significant role in this respect as it is known to affect overall life satisfaction. On the basis of the report published by the JOBHOUSE agency, Poles are moderately satisfied with their work (6.3 points on a scale of 10). As many as 88% of subjects believe that good pay leads to overall happiness, good relations with co-workers play an important role and the opportunities that work can offer in terms of professional development

form an important aspect of overall satisfaction [16].

The results of surveys conducted by Lisowska [12] among teachers confirm that life satisfaction increases along with job satisfaction. In both this study as well as in the research reported in this paper, statistically significant dependences between life satisfaction and gender of the interviewees were not established.

The study by Korczyński [11] demonstrated that 62% of teachers with a short length of service (up to 5 years) are characterized by a high level of professional satisfaction, in comparison to 46% of subjects reporting work satisfaction after 20 years of professional experience. According to the study by Cackowska and Szczepańska [1], the professional satisfaction of teachers depends on individual factors related to personality (needs, attitudes) as well as on aspects related to

performance at work in the professional environment (external motivators) including economic factors. We should bear in mind that most teachers in Poland (60%) are dissatisfied with both their level of prestige and with their income [6]. Despite this fact, the teaching profession is well regarded in society, and pedagogy courses are still commonly selected by young people [9]. Research concerned with the prestige of professions conducted in Poland demonstrates that the level of respect for teachers' work is ahead of scores recorded for doctors, attorneys, judges or policemen [15]. It also turns out that low salaries do not discourage teachers from taking up posts in their chosen profession, and this aspect plays an important role for only 7% of them. This willingness to work with young learners definitely determines the selection of this profession [2].

The study by Sekścińska and Maison [17] examined life satisfaction measured by the application of the SWLS test that was performed three times and employed a representative sample of adult Poles, and obtained an average score of 21 points, which is lower than the one that was recorded in the present study (24 points). We can therefore presume that the occupational role determines a higher level of life satisfaction in relation to the general population; however, this hypothesis requires a thorough verification in the study employing a representative sample of physical education teachers.

We can note with appreciation the fact that in this research over half of the surveyed teachers are characterized by a high level of life satisfaction. Some researchers prove that teacher satisfaction is capable of reliably predicting the creativity and organizational skills of an individual at school [4]. Happy teachers tend to work more efficiently, and give out positive energy and optimism, which are extremely important aspects in dealing with students, in particular in the context of the education of youth in order to strive for a healthy lifestyle.

Teachers, and in particular physical education teachers, should be characterized by their optimistic approach to life. Their main task

is to prepare for a good working life, to participate independently in physical culture, that is, a field which plays an important role in maintaining overall well-being. Its main domains include numerous challenges related to the body and well-being, including physical fitness and developing health potential. This sphere of free time is aimed at maximizing the ability to rest and regenerate after work. As a part of their social mission, teachers should perform the role of reflexive practitioners who not only pursue their profession, but also spread a passion that is employed to develop authority, and have considerable pedagogical influence [18].

Professional work forms just a single element in the creation of life satisfaction. However, we have to realize the challenges of the variety of ways in which it can be implemented and the sense of efficiency, which can be challenging for teachers in the context of professional work, since tangible effects (permanent changes in personality) can be forecast very often only after the completion of school education. Normally, teaching efforts (i.e. the transfer of knowledge and skills) can lead to progress in a relatively short time from the transfer of knowledge. However, the roles taken on by physical education teachers are concerned with participation in school sport along with their students.

Teachers guide their pupils in taking an active part in sports competitions where the competences obtained during the course of sports training are verified in a short time. From nationwide surveys, we can learn that most teachers display an orientation that promotes sport participation, and this does not necessarily promote health directly, which can be attributed to the search for professional as well as life satisfaction resulting from activity in sports [14]. Health education – which forms an important task imposed on teachers in the light of new legal regulations – does not provide equally easily measurable and objective outcomes of effort compared to involvement in the sports competition system.

The results of the research conducted for the purposes of this work demonstrate that a significant proportion of physical education

teachers, in the event of a potentially increased amount of free time, would spend it passively in a way that is free of considerable physical effort (53.5%). Apparently, the perceived exertion associated with professional activity is due to a known fact – the need to be fit most of the time. We can emphasize, however, that being fit forms a general life philosophy, that is, a way of life that focuses on activity and health, and permeates all dimensions of life, and determines above all the time remaining at the disposal of a person beyond their professional duties. Teachers who potentially plan to participate in physical activity in their free time also need to be supported at work on a daily basis, as they can be described as enthusiasts of the professional experience. The teachers of this course can serve to spread their professional role beyond work and, consequently, to encourage an active and healthy lifestyle in a more effective manner.

Undoubtedly, the lack of significant relationships of life satisfaction with selected occupational and socio-cultural factors found in this study can serve as a motivation for further exploration of other factors that can determine the life satisfaction of physical education teachers.

Conclusion

- The study did not demonstrate statistically significant differences in terms of the gender of the subjects, as well as in the level of education at which the surveyed teachers work in relation to their analyzed parameters. Most teachers demonstrate a high (55.6%) level of life satisfaction, whereas this level is at an average of 41.4%, and a low of 3%.
- There is no statistically significant relationship either between life satisfaction or age, work experience or time spent in a sitting position. Only 46.5% of the surveyed teachers stated that if they had more free time, they would select among others, engaging in some forms of physical activity. People who work longer hours more often state that they are willing to perform various forms of activities excluding physical activity.
- It seems necessary to encourage physical activity among physical education teachers as a way of spending free time. It would also be necessary to look for the factor responsible for life satisfaction among a variety of areas, not only socio-cultural and professional, but also economic, with a note that such research should involve a larger population of interviewees.

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